

Editor's message

The world of geography is varied and wonderful as revealed in the papers in this issue of the *South Australian Geographical Journal*—from hoof prints to community gardens to native vegetation to bridges to Lutheranism.

The study of hoof prints was a totally new concept for me, but on mentioning to a fellow Royal Geographical Society member how obscure but charming I found Helen Waudby and Sophie Petit's paper—the ultimate niche topic—the response was that people have written whole doctoral theses on the subject of hoof prints!

Community gardens are flourishing in South Australia and many of us would have visited them as part of the Open Gardens Australia Scheme, now rebadged as Open Gardens South Australia. But I didn't think of them as building community resilience, another new concept for me, as explained by Melissa Nursey-Bray and her colleagues. The landmark book she refers to, *Tomorrow: a peaceful path to real reform* reprinted as *Garden cities: a way forward* by Ebenezer Howard, can be read online.

Living in the Adelaide Hills I have a strong connection with the flora and fauna of stringybark forest so it is a shock to see evidence of how much vegetation clearance has occurred in the Mount Lofty Ranges since 1945. Andrew Lothian is passionate about landscape quality, and is following in the botanical/landscaping tradition of his father, former Adelaide Botanic Gardens director Noel Lothian, whose archival record group PRG 560 at the State Library of South Australia extends to some 11 metres of material, including 700 colour slides, generously made freely available to researchers for publication. Andrew's co-author Colin Harris is well known to Society members for his interest in, and publications on, native vegetation as well as other ecological topics, and of course, his pesky Christmas quizzes.

The indefatigable Richard Venus is a mine of useful and interesting pieces of information unearthed in his quest for knowledge about our engineering heritage. For Part 2 of his research on the River Torrens—friend and foe, he has comprehensively trawled the National Library of Australia's fabulous newspaper digitisation website *Trove* and other sources to track developments in the history of our bridges. As an example of Richard's incidental uncoverings, I was pleased to learn that Robert Gouger, one of my heroes, was referred to as Bob Gouger by Osmond Gilles in the *South Australian Gazette and Colonial Register* of 16 September 1837 on page 3. Richard informs me that he is still researching the other bridges over the Torrens, such as the Victoria and Albert, so the saga may continue in the next issue!

Rachel Kuchel is the Archivist and Director of the Lutheran Archives. She gave an entertaining and informative presentation to the Society, which she has adapted for publication in this *Journal*. I had no idea of the breadth of the Lutheran commitment to education and community development until I read Rachel's paper, and am pleased to reproduce it here to reach a wider audience. I am pleased to recall that with the Friends of the Heysen Trail, I walked the Pioneer Women's Trail recreating the feats of the German women carrying their produce from Hahndorf to the plains.

It is so sad that everyone's favourite demographer, Graeme Hugo AO is no longer with us. What a loss. John Connell makes us feel we know the man, in his beautifully written homage, including personal insights like Graeme's love for the Port Adelaide Football Club.

Editing the *South Australian Geographical Journal* for three years has been a rewarding experience and I am grateful for the professional opportunity, but have reluctantly decided I am not doing the role justice. It is probably the case that working people with a variety of interests competing for precious time, can only take on such roles for a few years at a time. Maybe in retirement I will put up my hand again. The *Journal* is now in the capable hands of Melissa Nursey-Bray, whose role in the Department of Geography, Environment and Population at the University of Adelaide makes her well placed to elicit contributions from the student and academic community which is the lifeblood of geographical research in South Australia.

Thank you and well done to the writers and reviewers of papers in this issue, to Alaric Maude for his wonderful company, lunches, editorial advice and assistance with the layout of the *Journal*, and to Rod, Dick and Margaret in the office for their friendship and support.

Most importantly, to you the readers, if you have a geographical project or research underway, consider writing it up for the *Journal* and send it to the new editor at melissa.nursey-bray@adelaide.edu.au so that your work can be enjoyed by others, and become part of the geographical record.

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